

Tourism activities related to silvopastoral systems: herder holiday, GreenCare, adventure holiday.
www.eurafagroforestry.eu/afinet/

In Finnish Lapland, rural tourism is well developed. It has an annual turnover of about 500-600 million euros providing employment to about 5000 persons. There would be plenty of opportunities for rural tourism in other parts of Finland too. The “herder holiday” has proven to be a very successful format. It gives people the chance to spend a holiday on a real farm and do some real farm work during the holiday. Many people claim they come back from their holiday as a different person. They are more relaxed, or they can even change their values what really matters in life. During the holiday they get certain duties in taking care of the animals and most people will carry out these duties very exactly. In this type of holiday there is of course also the possibility to enjoy, spend free time and time with the family and outdoor activities (hiking, canoeing, cycling). GreenCare is similar but more for therapy or groups of elderly people. An “adventure holiday” is also similar but more tailored for school kids or other groups of kids. Rural tourism goes together very well with traditional farms, traditional rural areas (agroforestry landscapes, e.g. wood pastures) and/or traditional livestock breeds. However, running a rural tourism farm doesn’t fit everyone. It fits for farmers with social skills for working with groups and who enjoy working with a lot of other people.

The same concept could be applied in other countries too. In this type of farming system, the farm probably gets less income from the normal farming activities and most income will come from tourist activities (rent of cottages, meals, organizing activities). Environmental payments (e.g. payments for management of key biotopes or rural landscapes) continue in the normal way.

Links

Rural tourism in Lapland [Poro on Lapin matkailun johtotähti] <https://paliskunnat.fi/poro/matkailu/>

Farms providing rural tourism services [Paimenlomat 2019]:

https://www.laidunpankki.fi/laidunpankki/haku.tmpl?sivu_id=282&l=1&navipath=283&lihantuottaja_arvot=Paimenlomat&haku=1

View in Koli. Photo by Michael den Herder

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